

RESEARCH ARTICLE

TRACING ISLAMIC HERITAGE IN THE JORDANIAN BADIA: PRELIMINARY REMARKS ON A NEWLY DISCOVERED MOSQUE

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Figure 1. A map of Jordan showing the location of Al-Khudari Mosque.

ABSTRACT. *The present paper investigates an Islamic mosque identified in the surveys of the Badia Epigraphic Survey (BES) Project in 2018. The mosque is located in the Wadi Al-Khudari area of the northeastern Jordanian Badia. The mosque is characterized by the significant height of its walls, the surrounding area of approximately 100 square meters,*

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and a variety of Arabic Islamic inscriptions. In addition to the construction techniques used and the unique architectural aspects of the mosque, this suggests significant historical and cultural value. The research suggests that the Islamic mosque in the Jordanian Badia can be categorized into two categories: temporary and permanent, segregating by architectural form and design.

KEYWORDS. Rock art, Black Desert, Jordanian Badia, written heritage, early Islamic architecture, OCIANA.

INTRODUCTION

The documentation of Ancient North Arabian (ANA) inscriptions has become an important area of research, with numerous advances having been made in the past decade relating to new technologies. One of the most remarkable innovations has been the introduction of the Global Positioning System (GPS) for the location of inscriptions and funerary cairns in the northeastern Jordanian Badia. The use of the GPS to assist in the documentation of such archaeological features has changed how these types of artifacts are studied and managed.

In 2017, the Online Corpus of the Inscriptions of Ancient North Arabia (OCIANA) was commenced, in part in response to surging demand for systematic documentation. These sites hosted over 30,000 inscriptions, some newly documented and some previously published. A result of the growing demand to document the inscriptions was a lack of accurate georeferencing, or geographical coordinates, for most inscriptions. Consequently, in 2015, Michael Macdonald and Ali Al-Manaser began the Badia Epigraphic Survey Project, which has become an ongoing endeavor to re-document the previously recorded inscriptions, as well as document new inscriptions. The project began using GIS mapping and continues to utilize advanced GPS technologies to gain accurate artifact localizations, which could then be inserted into the OCIANA database to add value and dependability as a research tool. In the last few years, we have been able to explore the Jordanian desert and take extensive surveys almost annually (Alhatlani & Al-Manaser 2022; Al-Manaser 2023; Al-Manaser & Macdonald 2024).

These systematic fieldwork campaigns have led to the discovery of thousands of previously undocumented inscriptions and the re-documentation of numerous inscriptions featured in scientific articles, books, and academic dissertations by both Jordanian and Western scholars. Despite the logistical challenges faced by desert survey teams, including extreme terrain, harsh climatic conditions, and the remoteness of many archaeologi-

cal sites, they have succeeded in reaching and systematically documenting previously unexplored regions. These efforts have yielded hundreds of unique inscriptions, including Palmyrene, Greek, and Nabataean texts, alongside thousands of newly identified Safaitic and early Arabic Islamic inscriptions. Among the most significant findings are inscriptions directly associated with early Islamic architectural sites, particularly mosques exhibiting key structural elements such as *mihrrabs* and prayer halls.

ARCHITECTURAL AND EPIGRAPHIC DISCOVERIES

The survey team identified an important architectural remnant, including mosques. The mosques could be categorized into two categories:

1. Permanent mosques were designed and are possibly pre-existing standardized built form types.
2. Temporary or emergency mosques were built quickly for funeral rites as a prayer enclosure made from simple stones with a small *mihrrab* (prayer niche) used during the funeral before being left behind.

These permanent mosques possessed important common architectural features, such as:

- Being close to water sources (natural springs and wells).
- They were constructed using multi-course stone masonry to ensure durability.
- Having standard dimensions.
- Having usable architectural features.

The BES has documented five main mosques, each distinguished by its architectural form and epigraphic content. These mosques are:

The Wadi Al-Sarar Mosque, which has approximately 40 Islamic inscriptions. The Wadi Salma Mosque, which has a similar number, and the two mosques documented in total in the same area, and the Al-Khudari Mosque (Figure 1), with around 100 Islamic Arabic inscriptions and dates from different times, also has 13 water wells. This makes it an even more interesting example, as it indicates the need for religious architec-

Figure 2. Site plan of Al-Khudari Mosque (Esraa Z. Hasan).

ture to be in proximity to water resources. Finally, there is the Al-Ghawanem Mosque, which is close to Tell Al-Masma.

In addition to these mosques, a selection of around 2,000 inscriptions from different Islamic periods was assembled, with the majority dating to the 7th and 8th centuries AH. These inscriptions provide a window into the historical, economic, and social conditions of the day (Macdonald & Al-Manaser 2017). Arabic-Islamic inscriptions are widespread in northern Badia, especially in places that are elevated, such as hills or highlands, and these inscriptions are often located near ancient North Arabian inscriptions. The choice of stony surfaces that were appropriate to inscribe suggests a precautionary approach from early Muslim inscribers, who frequently intentionally avoided disrupting pre-Islamic inscriptions, perhaps indicating cultural awareness or respectful regard for the written language of an earlier culture.

TEMPORARY VS. PERMANENT MOSQUES

The Badia Epigraphic Survey (BES) Project surveys conducted in the Jordanian Badia revealed numerous small and simple mosques, with a more precise designation as temporary mosques or emergency mosques. These mosques were clearly built for short-duration use, usually during a funeral. The following features were associated with temporary mosques:

- Typically located near burial cairns to provide a prayer space.

- Built with uncomplicated arrangements of stones, including a small *mihrab*.

- Often abandoned after a very short period of use.

- Some burial sites had two mosques, one on each side of the grave, which could indicate a separation of men and women for prayer. Except for the few you saw defined in the site presentations and walks, most mosques, with a permanent structure are fewer and have distinctly different architectural features and functions.

KEY ASPECTS OF PERMANENT MOSQUES

1. *Wall Height*: Constructed of stone masonry in stacked courses, with a minimum height of one meter.

2. *Mihrab*: Clearly indicated and situated within the *qibla* wall.

3. *Standardized Dimensions*: A standardized dimension that is close in size (generally within a range of 11 × 11 m) and has a distinguishable entrance.

4. *Close to Water*: Positioned near a pond or a bunch of wells that had long-term usability.

5. *Located at a Strategic Location*: Built on the edge of a valley so that individuals could often enter without delay in getting to water collection points.

6. *Decoration*: The most common feature of all mosques was stone carving, and almost all had stone around the *qibla* area. Carved stone decoration features were frequently noted as a contrast to religious architecture; the carved stone designs functioned as epigraphic traces.

AL-KHUDARI MOSQUE

The Badia Epigraphic Survey Project Team conducted fieldwork in Wadi Al-Khudari, the major northeastern Jordanian Badia region, between 2018 and 2024, one of the larger areas studied. The name Wadi Al-Khudari is derived from the rich green that arises in spring and persists for a long time. Wadi Al-Khudari is approximately 15 km in length, from the Hamad area to the Akhdari Wells, and produced a large collection of ANA. One of the major archaeological finds in the region is an Islamic mosque uncovered in the Wadi Al-Khudari Wells area. Nearby is a water pool and a major cairn containing over 2,000 Safaitic inscriptions and rock art. It was noted that the mosque was constructed in an open, flat area, near the location of many sheep pen areas, which helped support the use of the mosque for residents as well as visitors from other areas. The mosque can be accessed from two separate roads: one road is from Wadi Hashad Al-Khudari, while the other road is from the area of Tel Al-Hafit. The mosque is located at the entrance to Wadi Al-Khudari from the west; thus, anyone who wishes to enter the valley from that area will have to pass through this mosque.

The Mosque's Architectural Features and Site Selection

The Al-Khudari Mosque (Figures 3 & 4) is illustrative of the elements of traditional dry-stone sustainable architecture, which incorporated structural changes in response to the surrounding area and socio-cultural needs of the area. The site's location and adjacent features suggest that it functioned as more than a mere prayer house. It would have served as a seasonal resting area for travelers and the nomadic tribes of the area, too.

Geographical and Environmental Considerations

From a geographical perspective, the mosque is strategically positioned near a valley containing approximately 13 water wells, reinforcing its significance as a key settlement point in the region. This proximity to water suggests that the mosque may have been used seasonally, particularly during periods of rainfall and water accumulation in the valley. To the right of the mosque, the valley features a natural water collection area, capable of retaining water for nearly three months after rainfall. This natural reservoir would have made

the location an attractive meeting point for passing tribes and travelers, further supporting the idea that the mosque was intermittently used rather than serving as a permanent religious institution.

Given its location, the mosque may have facilitated several key religious functions, including:

- *Funeral Prayers*: The presence of water sources could indicate its use as a site for funeral rites and ritual purification (*ghusl*) of the deceased.
- *Friday Prayers*: The site's accessibility and central position suggest that it may have served as a temporary Friday prayer site, accommodating nearby Bedouin communities.
- *Seasonal Worship*: The mosque may have functioned as a seasonal place of congregation, activated during rainy periods when water availability made longer stays possible.

Religious and Economic Integration in Desert Architecture

The Al-Khudari Mosque design reflects an unusual interaction between the spiritual and economic aspects of life and indicates how religious sites were purposefully created to address the needs of nomadic societies. The presence of a mosque and hunting enclosures indicates that Bedouins possibly utilized the site as a temporary resting site during hunting and herding trips, mixing worship with daily survival-related tasks. This supports a larger idea about the construction of early Islamic mosques in desert settings—that religious structures were places of prayer but were also multifunctional places that addressed a range of social, economic, and logistical needs.

Architectural Characteristics and Temporary Nature of the Mosque

The architecture of the mosque demonstrates that it was not built according to proper geometric plans. The enclosed area, roughly square, was a space surrounded by basalt stones that did not line up neatly and had a small *mihrab* (a praying niche) facing the *qibla* direction. Since it was built simply, the mosque was probably roofed with some form of lightweight temporary material, such as fabric or woven materials, especially for seasonal use. These features lend strong support to the idea that the mosque was not a permanent building but rather a seasonal or temporary prayer space that was used occasionally by other tribes and travelers.

Figure 3. Site plan of Al-Khudari Mosque (Esraa Z. Hasan).

Figure 4. Imaginary image of the stakes and the mosque (Esraa Z. Hasan).

Interior Features and Structural Evidence of Temporary Roofing

An examination of the interior space of the mosque reveals the presence of circular depressions within the ground that would have acted as support for wooden posts to hold a temporary roof. This type of roofing material, generally made of goat hair fabric similar to that of traditional Bedouin tents, would have offered both shade from the sun and protection for users. It also allowed for easy taking down of the structure when not in use. Since the surrounding landscape was predominantly occupied by nomadic Bedouins, it is logical that the mosque acted as a place for open-air prayer and worship purposes, with a roof being optional. However, the actual mortar around the potential columns suggests temporary or removable roofs were available for use on specific occasions, such as:

- Friday prayers where shaded gathering was necessary for congregation.
- Seasonal religious gatherings during periods of rain and temporary availability of water.

Conceptual Reconstruction of the Mosque

A conceptual reconstruction of the mosque envisions it as a prayer space in the open air, surrounded by low walls made of irregular basalt stones (Figures 5 & 6). In another image (Figure 3), you can observe wooden pillars located in the center of the mosque, with a canopy of fabric suspended from the pillars, similar to the burlap or goat-hair materials that are used in tensed Bedouin tents. Finally, the mosque is imagined as constructed with lightweight and easily handled materials. Again supporting the proposition that Islamic religious buildings in desert climates, and where communities may be nomadic in their lifestyle, reflected a design concept focused on mobility and practicality.

Architectural Evidence and Construction Methods

This mosque has preserved the precepts of traditional dry-stone architecture, which was modified accordingly by local environmental conditions. This was evidenced by the use of stones stacked without mortar, indicating a sophisticated understanding of material properties from local knowledge and practical needs. Dry-stone constructions were found more commonly in shale or mountainous areas because of the availability of stones

that could endure them. On the contrary, few dry-stone buildings could be found in areas where limestone or other building materials were available since builders tended to use more refined masonry techniques.

Dry-Stone Construction in the Northern Desert

In the northern Badia regions, dry-stone construction relied heavily on locally available basalt rocks, which dominate the landscape. These black basalt stones were manually gathered from the surrounding terrain, carefully stacked to create structurally stable walls without the use of mortar or cement, and arranged in irregular, polygonal forms. They adapt to the natural shapes of the stones rather than imposing geometric precision. This method provided several structural advantages, including increased stability through the interlocking of stones, natural resistance to thermal expansion and contraction, reduced structural stress in extreme desert temperatures, and high durability. This enabled the structures to withstand wind erosion and seismic activity.

Structural Features of the Mosque

The mosque's massive walls exhibit an organic, flowing construction style, distinct from the rigid, straight-line geometry of later architectural traditions. The irregular stacking of stones may have served functional purposes, such as enhancing structural stability, particularly in an environment prone to strong desert winds, and providing natural buttressing, reinforcing the walls against erosion and collapse over time. One of the most significant architectural features of the mosque is the presence of inscriptions, particularly on the southern wall, where the *mihrab* (prayer niche) is located. The varied orientations of these inscriptions indicate that the stones were likely repurposed from older structures rather than being inscribed specifically for this mosque. This suggests that the reuse of building materials was a common practice, reflecting both practical resource management and the continuity of architectural traditions in the region (Figures 7 & 8).

BETWEEN INSCRIPTIONS AND ARCHITECTURE

The connection between inscriptions and Islamic architecture in the Jordanian Badia presents a unique

Figure 5. Detail of the south facade wall at Al-Khudari Mosque (Esraa Z. Hasan).

Figure 6. The mosque walls.

strand of early Islamic cultural manifestation. Much research has been conducted with the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan about early Islamic mosques in its southern and northern regions, but little investigation has

occurred in the northeastern desert due to its seclusion and distance from large urban centers (Al-Bqain 2004; Al-Bqain *et al.* 2015). Some scholars have researched the phenomenon of open mosques in their works on

Figure 7. Al-Khudari Mosque.

early Islamic architecture in Jordan, where an “open” mosque is a specific form of mosque in the discussion with the notion of it as a mosque in Jordan (Jarrar 2024; Rjoub & Al-Housan 2013; Weber-Karyotakis *et al.*

2020). However, what identifies the mosques of the northeastern Jordanian desert is their preponderance of Islamic inscriptions, either as verses of the Quran, prophetic traditions (*hadiths*), or supplications. These

Figure 8. Permanent and temporary mosques.

inscriptions mostly show up on the southern wall of the mosque, i.e., the location of the *mihrab* and *qibla*. It may have been normal custom, a method of blessing the mosque, and perhaps to leave a spiritual index in that space.

Inscriptions containing Quranic verses, supplications, and prophetic *hadiths* establish an additional spiritual connection, with the mosque acquiring an aura of sacredness that renders it untouchable. As a result, most mosques with inscriptions are presumed to be destroyed as a result of neglect and abandonment and not deliberate desecration, in spite of the fact that it seems a large portion of the destruction came about as a result of deliberate vandalism (such as destroying or defacing a mosque with inscriptions). Interestingly, it appears that stones inscribed with Quranic verses were often placed at higher locations in these buildings, possibly as an attempt at protection, whether by worshippers or visitors alike, given their spiritual content.

The Islamic inscriptions in the Jordanian Badia propose significant historical implications regarding the migration/settlement patterns relating to the northward or southward movement of tribal groups. Inscriptions also denote human terrestrial activity in the Jordanian Harrah, even though no permanent architecture has survived; therefore, settlement activity would have been denser in the interior and closer to southern Syria. Urban centers would then refer to towns like Sweida, Salkhad, Bosra al-Sham, and Umm al-Quttin and Umm al-Jimal in Jordan. Inscriptions are then archaeological markers that reconstruct the social and cultural landscapes of the area in the Islamic period.

CONCLUSION

The architectural and epigraphical assessment of the Al-Khudari Mosque and associated buildings demonstrates a sense of Islamic religious architecture in the Jordanian Badia. The employment of basalt stone, a local material, and dry-stone masonry consoles an environmentally adjusted construction type using available resources.

Epigraphical analysis of inscriptions, found to be on reused stone pieces, indicates the alteration of previous buildings, which also illustrates cultural endurance or modification over time. These structures acted not just as places of worship but also as social gatherings for travelers and herders and connected economic activities within the badia. The dry-stone configuration of the Al-Khudari Mosque was a clear reactionary form to the

desert, where irregular stones helped create a stable structure without the use of mortar. The location and variability of water sources, as well as the lack of permanent roofing, all suggest the use of the mosque was intermittent, primarily for congregational Friday prayers or funeral rites.

The abundance of Islamic inscriptions surrounding the *mihrab* emphasized its sacredness and offered a link to wider Islamic traditions. The reuse of carved stones indicated some structural history of architectures that were adapted into existent spaces. The elevation and location of the mosque, as well as the configuration and materials incorporated into the dry-stone technique, provided a better understanding of the evolution of Islamic religious architecture in an arid landscape.

Further archaeological studies and epigraphical and environmental analyses are needed if we are to develop more nuanced narratives of Islamic life within marginal landscapes so we might understand how Muslim societies adapted their collective culture and displayed their architectural ingenuity.

REFERENCES

- AL-BQAIN, F. 2004. *Dirasah li-masjid shirah wa-masajid umawiyah mumathilah fi janub al-urdun*. Unpublished MA thesis. University of Jordan.
- AL-BQAIN, F. *ET ALII*. 2015. An Umayyad Era Mosque and Desert Waystation from Wadi Shireh, Southern Jordan. *Journal of Islamic Archaeology* 2(1): 93–126.
- ALHATLANI, A.S.; A. AL-MANASER. 2022. The Harrah's epigraphic heritage: Arabic graffito from the Black Desert in north-eastern Jordan referring to the Umayyad caliph Hisham b. Abd al-Malik. *Arabian Archaeology and Epigraphy* 33(1): 216–225.
- AL-MANASER, A. 2023. Documenting Jordan's epigraphic heritage: Preliminary remarks on newly discovered Safaitic inscriptions. *Arabian Archaeology and Epigraphy* 34(1): 173–182.
- AL-MANASER, A.; M.C.A. MACDONALD. 2024. Ancient and modern inscriptions in the basalt desert: News from the 2023 season of the Badia Epigraphic Survey in north-east Jordan. *Arabian Archaeology and Epigraphy* 35(1): 218–235.
- AL-MANASER, A.; L. ELLIS. 2018. New Islamic inscriptions from the Jordanian Badia region. *Arabian Epigraphic Notes* 4: 69–86.
- JARRAR, N. 2024. Developing digital Islamic heritage sites in Jordan: The case of al-Mafraq. *Digital Applications in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage* 32: e00316.

- MACDONALD, M.C.A.; A. AL-MANASER. 2017. Report on the Wadi Salma area epigraphic survey, April 2015. *Bulletin for the Council for British Research in the Levant* 12(1): 36–39.
- MACDONALD, M.C.A.; A. AL-MANASER. 2019. Recording Graffiti in the Black Desert: Past, Present, and Future. *Journal of Eastern Mediterranean Archaeology and Heritage Studies* 7(2): 205–222.
- RJOUB, A.; A. AL-HOUSAN. 2013. Architecture of Heritage Mosques in Mafraq Province. *International Journal of Architectural Heritage* 7(4): 461–478.
- WEBER-KARYOTAKIS, T.M. ET ALII, EDS. 2020. *Islamic Heritage Sites in Jordan: A Student's Gazetteer*. School of Architecture and Built Environment (SABE), German Jordanian University.